

Dynamic model of a power-to-gas system: Role of hydrogen storage and management strategies

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ABSTRACT

Tackling climate change requires a drastic decarbonization of the energy system through the introduction of renewable energy technologies. However, a greater penetration of intermittent renewables requires large-scale flexible energy storage. This need, combined with the growing interest in the use of hydrogen in mobility and industry, makes tangible the prospect of including this energy vector in our daily lives. However, the problems related to the development of dedicated infrastructures make its positioning in the market complex. In a transition phase, power-to-gas systems constitute an emerging solution that allows the use of existing structures for natural gas and, at the same time, solves the problem of hydrogen storage. In this study, a power-to-gas system producing synthetic methane from wind energy was modeled. Management strategies for both the electrolysis system and the hydrogen storage were implemented. In particular, the impact of the storage on the mitigation of the operating condition fluctuation of the methanation unit was analyzed. To verify the influence of the sizing of the subsystems over the system performance, a sensitivity analysis on the sizes of the methanation unit and hydrogen storage was carried out. The conducted sensitivity analysis suggested selecting the smallest size of the hydrogen storage and the size of the methanation unit equal to 80% of the electrolysis system nominal production to achieve good performances of the power-to-gas system. However, the sizing of the subsystems depends on the context in which the power-to-gas system is integrated (i.e., characteristics of wind source), the possibility to valorize the hydrogen surplus (i.e., proximity to hydrogen users), and the specific objective for which the system has been designed.

1. Introduction

The decarbonization of energy systems requires the use of green and Renewable Energy Sources (RES). However, the high penetration of RES in the global energy mix creates additional challenges related to the more complex management of energy flows and the difficulty of matching energy demand and production. Verzijlbergh et al. [1] face the major challenges related to the high integration of RES into the European energy system, both from a technological and institutional point of view. They conclude that the substantial interdependence between these two aspects requires a more integrated approach to solve the problems related to the variability and unpredictability of RES. In particular, they claim that the transition to an energy system based on RES requires a combination of flexible generation capacity, energy storage, demand

response and grid interconnection, and identify chemical storage through hydrogen as a viable possibility. Nevertheless, today 96% of the produced hydrogen is obtained from fossil fuels and only 3.9% comes from electrolysis [2] due to the elevated costs associated with its entire supply chain. Although some hydrogen production technologies alternative to fossil fuel-based ones are already mature, the lack of dedicated infrastructures makes the introduction of hydrogen in the market difficult [3]. A 2–5%_{vol} hydrogen blending threshold in the current natural gas grid may be adopted without major technical or regulatory interventions at the transmission and distribution level [5] while a 15–20%_{vol} threshold is potentially applicable from 2030 without major adaptation of the existing gas infrastructure, but may require modifications of end-use appliances [4,5]. According to Ref. [5], with a 20% threshold, up to 40–70.8 GW of electrolyzer capacity could be integrated

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on a European scale. Nevertheless, the large scale implementation of hydrogen blending poses issues with safety and embrittlement [6]. Using hydrogen for the synthesis of various hydrocarbons, including methane [7,8] could be considered a viable solution to foster the hydrogen economy while using the existing infrastructure. To further bolster this thesis, Gallo et al. [9] analyze and compare twenty-eight alternatives of energy storage systems and conclude that there is no optimal storage system in an absolute sense, but that selection must be made on a case-by-case basis. However, in the context of the energy transition, where seasonal storage is necessary, they identify Power-to-Gas (P2G), Power-to-Liquid (P2L) and Solar-to-Fuel (S2F) systems as the most suitable solutions, as they can integrate different energy markets. In particular, P2G systems (both off-grid and on-grid systems) are considered promising for the development of more efficient and flexible energy systems for storing energy and using CO₂ [10], for the reduction of polluting emissions, and the increase of sustainability in sectors such as industry and mobility [8]. Europe, led by Germany, Denmark and Switzerland, is a leader in their implementation [10,11].

Bargiacchi et al. [12] model and compare four hydrogen conversion pathways for the production of energy carriers such as methane, methanol, ammonia, and urea based on energy and exergy efficiency and net carbon emissions. Sabatier process for methane production is found to be the most efficient. Methanation technologies show the potential to further improve efficiency, while optimizing the use of by-products such as oxygen and heat can help increase economic efficiency [11,12]. In addition, capital expenditures for different electrolysis and methanation technologies are expected to fall to around €500/kW_{el} in the long term [11].

The first question to address when discussing P2G systems involves establishing the electricity source to utilize. Gahleitner [7] offers an extensive overview of various P2G pilot plants using different energy sources. The most used sources coupled with P2G systems are wind and solar energy. Specifically, 24% of the plants examined are powered by electricity from the public grid, while the remaining are directly linked to RES.

After a comparison among short-term storage systems, Belderbos et al. [13] conclude that Power-to-Fuel (P2F) systems can play a significant role in scenarios with a high share of RES. In particular, they analyze four case studies, each of which is characterized by a different type of RES (onshore wind, offshore wind, or solar). Their study illustrates the different trends of methane production and how the role of P2G systems becomes more important when the renewable production profile has a seasonal trend. Also, Walker et al. [14] identify P2F as an attractive solution, especially for seasonal storage.

Synthetic natural gas (SNG) can be referred to as renewable or green only if it is carbon neutral. This requires not only that the electricity source used in the production process is carbon neutral but also that the CO₂ produced during its utilization is recycled to produce new methane or captured and stored [13]. Therefore, the selection of the CO₂ source is the second critical aspect that requires careful consideration.

Schiebahn et al. [3] explore various sources of CO₂ for P2G systems, including fossil power plants, biomass, industrial processes, and air. They discuss the advantages and disadvantages associated with each source. Generally, it is economically advantageous to use sources with higher concentrations of CO₂ [15]. This is because the costs associated with capturing CO₂ are lower for sources with higher concentrations. As a result, air as a source of CO₂ is less promising due to the higher associated costs (1.46 €/m³ of methane).

Another promising source of CO₂ is biogas. Using biogas allows for the possibility of utilizing heat from the methanation process and oxygen from electrolysis [16]. For example, the heat produced by the Methanation Unit (MU) can be used to heat an anaerobic digester, while surplus hydrogen can be used to upgrade biomethane.

Bargiacchi et al. [17] identify the most suitable CO₂ sources for Carbon Capture Utilization (CCU) for SNG production from a Life Cycle

Assessment (LCA) perspective. After a comparison between the environmental impacts of a large variety of CO₂ sources, they concluded that capturing CO₂ from hydrogen production plants and integrated pulp and paper mills led to the lowest impacts concerning all the investigated indicators.

A third crucial aspect of P2G systems is the choice of the electrolysis process. In general, alkaline electrolyzers (AELs) are more suitable for stationary applications, while Polymer Electrolyte Membrane (PEM) technologies offer better performance with intermittent and fluctuating power sources in terms of pressurized operation, flexibility, shorter start-up times, hydrogen purity, and the possibility to operate at full load range [18]. Indeed, AELs have some limitations on the lower operating load because of safety reasons, and they can generally operate in a range of 20–100% of the nominal power [16]. Nonetheless, AELs seem to sufficiently meet the flexibility needs of P2G systems [19], and alkaline electrolysis is currently the only available technology for higher capacities, with 67% of implemented P2G pilot projects utilizing AELs [7]. This prevalence is attributed to alkaline electrolysis being the most mature technology—both in terms of cost-effectiveness and development.

However, when directly coupling an Electrolysis System (ES) with variable RES, some issues arise and should be addressed. The variability of these sources might affect the system operation by causing frequent shutdowns, part-load, and dynamic operation. In turn, frequent shutdowns can accelerate stack degradation and should be limited. In addition, the intermittent RES availability causes a low number of annual equivalent operating hours that negatively affect the specific production cost of hydrogen. Several studies investigated the techno-economic aspects of ES coupled with RES. Liponi et al. [20] investigate the effect of the electrolyzer size on the levelized cost of hydrogen in the case of PV-electrolyzer coupling. The choice of the electrolyzer size should be a trade-off between the maximization of hydrogen production and the need for limiting shutdowns and having sufficiently high electrolyzer utilization factors to minimize the specific production costs. The possibility of adopting electric storage [21] and/or grid-electricity support [22] to mitigate wind variability has also been investigated. On one side, by allowing grid support, the electrolyzer operation can be continuous, and annual operating hours increase, resulting in a reduction of specific production costs. On the other side, if the electricity grid is not completely decarbonized, the carbon footprint of the so-produced hydrogen is higher. Another way to increase the flexibility of ESs coupled to variable sources is by considering separated electrolysis units, as studied in the case of a wind source [23]. This choice enables the ES to operate within a broader power range and allows for a reduction in on/off cycles per electrolyzer. The higher the number of separated electrolysis units, the higher the flexibility. However, decreasing the size of each unit increases the specific capital costs. Therefore, a trade-off between flexibility and costs must be found.

In multi-stack ESs, the choice of the management strategy for power allocation is crucial since it affects the system stability, overall efficiency, and stack lifetime. As reviewed by Lu et al. [24], one of the main conventional strategies is the average-allocation strategy, in which a constant number of electrolyzers are put into operation and the system input power is equally allocated to each single stack. Instead, in the daisy-chain allocation strategy, single stacks are put into operation one by one, with the previous electrolyzer reaching rated power before starting the next one, and so on [24]. A third option is to consider the optimal efficiency and determine the number of operating electrolyzers based on the maximization of the efficiency (optimal-efficiency strategy) and equally distribute the system input power to each operating stack [24]. Under the average-allocation strategy, the degradation of each stack is consistent, but system efficiency is not considered, and the overall operating load range of the system is lower. Although the optimal-efficiency strategy ensures maximum system efficiency, the electrolyzers may experience frequent on/off cycles, particularly during low wind speed periods. In addition, since this strategy evenly allocates input power among the electrolyzers in operation, it results in a higher variability of the

Fig. 1. Schematic representation of the P2G system [30].

electrolyzers' power input. Instead, the operating conditions of stacks under daisy-chain allocation are widely different from one another, which tends to increase the non-uniformity in the operation and degradation rate of the stacks. All these strategies have both positive and negative aspects, whose significance can vary depending on the characteristics of the variable energy source that supplies the system. Lu et al. [24] propose the optimization of a power allocation strategy for a wind-hydrogen system with a multi-stack PEM electrolyzer by considering degradation in five different operating conditions (maintaining, low power fluctuation, constant turning power, high power fluctuation, and constant rated power). The proposed strategy shows an energy efficiency that is comparable to the optimal-efficiency allocation strategy. Meanwhile, the single-stack degradation is similar among the stacks and lower than the stack degradation obtained with other power allocation strategies. Zheng et al. [25] propose a power allocation strategy which considers both the system energy efficiency and stack degradation. This strategy represents a trade-off between maximizing hydrogen production and maximizing stack lifetime, with the results showing the highest consolidated revenue.

Nevertheless, the discussion regarding the importance of a management strategy should not be confined solely to the electrolysis system but can be expanded to the entire P2G system, in particular when an intermediate Hydrogen Storage (HS) system is employed to decouple the ES and the MU. Baccioli et al. [26] analyze the costs associated with the production and sale of liquefied methane and oxygen from a P2G plant associated with a CO₂ source from a geothermal plant. This study reveals that using HS does not increase the cost-effectiveness of the plant, while "only small storage systems will be needed for managing the different dynamic behavior of the components" [26]. Gorre et al. also published two studies on this subject [27,28]. In the first one, they observe that the production costs of methane in a P2G system can be reduced by releasing the operation of the electrolyzer and MU by using an intermediate HS. In

In particular, the operational variables that are mostly influenced by the choice of subsystem sizes should be identified once the appropriate management strategy has been selected. In the present work, a mathematical model to simulate the operation of a P2G system coupled with wind energy is proposed. The issues related to the source variability are addressed by developing a management strategy for both the ES and the HS to limit the number of shutdowns (and consequently the equipment degradation) and, at the same time, to optimally exploit the electricity produced by the wind farm. A modular approach is adopted for the ES to increase its operational flexibility, while a sensitivity analysis is conducted on the size of the MU and the HS to evaluate the influence of subsystem sizes on the performance of the P2G system. The obtained results provide guidelines to size the subsystems based on the performance trends of selected indicators.

2. Modeling

In this study, the main components of the system are modeled, namely the wind farm and the P2G system.

2.1. Wind farm

The source of the wind speed data utilized for the simulations is the Wind Prospector tool of the National Renewable Energy Laboratory (NREL) website [29]. This tool provides data on wind resources and NREL models for analyzing the potential of wind energy. The wind speed data used are 5-min-averaged and specifically pertain to a windy location to ensure a high-capacity factor of the wind farm.

The wind farm is composed of eight turbines of 1.5 MW each. The turbine power is determined based on the given wind speed values as follows [22]:

$$P_t(t) = \begin{cases} \text{Oif } w_{\text{wind}}(t) < w_{\text{cutin}} \text{ Or } w_{\text{wind}}(t) > w_{\text{cutoff}} \\ -4.073 \bullet w_{\text{wind}}(t)^3 + 92.069 \bullet w_{\text{wind}}(t)^2 - 442.44 \bullet w_{\text{wind}}(t) + 647.68 & \text{if } w_{\text{cutin}} \leq w_{\text{wind}}(t) \leq w_r \\ -4.073 \bullet w_r^3 + 92.069 \bullet w_r^2 - 442.44 \bullet w_r + 647.68 & \text{if } w_r < w_{\text{wind}}(t) < w_{\text{cutoff}} \end{cases}$$

the second one, they underline the need to optimize the MU size to reduce production costs, depending on the operation strategy and the case study.

Thus, further investigation is needed to assess the impact of the management strategy of hydrogen surplus on the mitigation of the operating condition fluctuation of the MU, as well as the impact of the sizing of the main subsystems (MU and HS) on the system performances.

where $w_{\text{cutin}} = 3$ m/s is the cut-in velocity, $w_{\text{cutoff}} = 25$ m/s is the cut-off velocity, and $w_r = 11$ m/s is the rated velocity of the turbine.

2.2. Power-to-Gas system

The P2G system is composed of an ES (that consists of four AELs,

Fig. 2. Alkaline water electrolyzer process diagram [30].

Table 1

Parameters of the electrolyzer stack model [36].

Parameter	Unit	Value
Number of cells	–	326
Cell lateral area	m ²	2.66
Cell-block diameter	m	1.84
Free cell volume	m ²	0.027
Distance between bipolar plates	m	0.01
Stack length	m	5.85

each with a nominal power of 3 MW), a MU, and an intermediate HS system (see Fig. 1). The first step is the production of hydrogen (and oxygen) through an ES powered by a dedicated wind farm. The produced hydrogen is partly sent to the MU (where the conversion of hydrogen and CO₂ into methane takes place) and partly injected into an HS system for later usage by the MU. It should be noted that, while in this study only the main components of the system were modeled, other auxiliary components are required for the proper functioning of the system. These include power electronics for electrolyzer electricity feed-in, compressors for hydrogen and methane, and purification units for water and CO₂. The main components of the system are modeled as described below.

2.2.1. Alkaline electrolyzer

Several models for the simulation of the operation of an AEL are provided in the literature. One of the most used is the model proposed by Ulleberg [31], which is based on a combination of fundamental thermodynamics, heat transfer theory, and empirical electrochemical relationships. An extension of this model is proposed by Amores et al. [32] in which the effects of electrolyte concentration and cell architecture are also studied. Sánchez et al. published two other relevant studies on this subject [33,34] in which a semi-empirical mathematical model based on the polarization curve and the Faraday efficiency in dependence of pressure, temperature, and current density is proposed. Diéguez et al. [35] develop thermal modeling of the electrolyzer focusing on coupling the stack with a renewable energy source.

Whereas the above-mentioned studies use a simplified lumped parameter configuration for the description of the electrolyzer, in which stack, gas-liquid separators, and heat exchangers are treated as a single component, in this study a more detailed modeling is performed, paying

greater attention to individual elements and control systems. The baseline study used is from Sakas et al. [36] in which a model based on energy and mass balances with adjustable parameters with a zero-dimensional approach is proposed.

Electric current powers the stack for the production of gaseous hydrogen and oxygen according to the reaction:

At the stack outlet, a mixture of electrolyte (25 wt% KOH) and hydrogen on one side, and oxygen on the other side, is sent to the horizontal gas-liquid separators. Hydrogen and oxygen are removed from the separator, while the electrolyte mixture is sent to the mixer where it is mixed with the make-up water. The oxygen leaving the separator is just flushed from the process, while the produced hydrogen is sent to the MU (see Fig. 2).

The stack was modeled in Matlab assuming the parameters listed in Table 1. A thermal model and an electrochemical model were used to calculate the production of hydrogen, the trend of flow rates, temperatures, energy losses, cell voltage, and cell current.

2.2.1.1. Electrochemical submodel. The cell voltage is calculated as the sum of the reversible potential and overvoltage terms (Eq. (1)):

$$E_{\text{cell}} = E_{\text{rev}} + E_{\text{act}} + E_{\text{ohm}} + E_{\text{conc}} \quad (1)$$

The reversible potential is the minimum voltage necessary for the water-splitting reaction to take place and depends on the temperature and pressure according to the Nernst equation (Eq. (2)):

$$E_{\text{rev}} = E_{\text{rev}}^{\circ} + \frac{R \cdot T(\text{K})}{zF} \cdot \ln \left(\frac{(P - P_{\text{v,KOH}}) \cdot (P - P_{\text{v,KOH}})^{0.5}}{a_{\text{H}_2\text{O,KOH}}} \right) \quad (2)$$

The term $P_{\text{v,KOH}}$ is the vapour pressure of the solution, $a_{\text{H}_2\text{O,KOH}}$ is the water activity of the KOH solute, and the logarithmic term depends on the non-ideality of the process in terms of pressure. E_{rev}° is the standard reversible potential, which can be calculated through an empirical expression (Eq. (3)):

$$E_{\text{rev}}^{\circ} = 1.5184 - 1.5421 \cdot 10^{-3} \cdot T(\text{K}) + 9.526 \cdot 10^{-5} \cdot T(\text{K}) \cdot \ln(T(\text{K})) + 9.84 \cdot 10^{-8} \cdot (T(\text{K}))^2 \quad (3)$$

Ohmic and activation overvoltages are expressed through semi-empirical expressions as a function of temperature and current density [36] (Eqs. (4) and (5)):

$$E_{ohm} = \alpha \cdot i_{cell} = (\alpha_1 + \alpha_2 T) \cdot i_{cell} \quad (4)$$

$$E_{act} = s \cdot \log(\beta \cdot i_{cell} + 1) = s \cdot \log \left[\left(\beta_1 + \frac{\beta_2}{T} + \frac{\beta_3}{T^2} \right) \cdot i_{cell} + 1 \right] \quad (5)$$

In Eq. (4) and Eq. (5) the term i_{cell} is the current density, while parameters α_1 , α_2 , s , β_1 , β_2 , and β_3 need to be experimentally determined. Generally, industrial AELs operate at low cell current densities, so concentration overvoltage is generally minimal and can often be disregarded [36].

The polarization curve is defined as a function of the cell current, which is calculated through Newton's iterative method using the parameters adopted by Sakas et al. [36] for a 3 MW AEL.

2.2.1.2. Thermal submodel. The stack operating temperature ($T_{stack}(t)$) of an AEL has a strong influence on its performance [18]. A lumped thermal capacitance model is adopted as done by Sakas et al. [36].

The overall energy balance over the control volume represented by the stack [37] is expressed by (Eq. (6)):

$$C_{stack} \cdot dT_{stack}(t)/dt = Q_{gen}(t) - Q_{loss}(t) + \dot{m}_{lye}(t) \cdot \bar{c}_{p,lye} \cdot (T_{lye,cool,out}(t) - T_{stack}(t)) \quad (6)$$

The term on the left in Eq. (6) represents the rate of change of the electrolyzer temperature over time, while Q_{gen} (Eq. (7)) is the heat generated inside the stack, Q_{loss} (Eq. (8)) is the total heat loss to the ambient and the other two terms are the enthalpy flows of the incoming ($\dot{m}_{lye}(t) \cdot \bar{c}_{p,lye} \cdot T_{lye,cool,out}(t)$) and outgoing ($\dot{m}_{lye}(t) \cdot \bar{c}_{p,lye} \cdot T_{stack}(t)$) electrolyte mixture from the stack.

$$Q_{gen}(t) = n_{cell} \cdot (E_{cell}(t) - E_{tm}) \cdot I(t) \quad (7)$$

$$Q_{loss}(t) = \frac{T_{stack}(t) - T_{amb}}{R_{stack}} \quad (8)$$

where R_{stack} is the stack thermal resistance.

The water consumption flow rate in the stack $\dot{m}_{wat,cons}(t)$ can be calculated through the stoichiometry of the water splitting reaction as in Eqs. (9) and (10):

$$\dot{m}_{wat,cons}(t) = \dot{n}_{wat,cons}(t) \cdot MM_{wat} \quad (9)$$

$$\dot{n}_{wat,cons}(t) = \dot{n}_{H_2}(t) \quad (10)$$

where $\dot{n}_{H_2}(t)$ is the molar hydrogen production and can be calculated as a function of the stack current $I(t)$, the total number of cells n_{cell} , the Faraday efficiency η_F , the Faraday constant $F = 96485$ C/mol and the number of electrons transferred in the water-splitting reaction ($z = 2$) (Eq. (11)):

$$\dot{n}_{H_2}(t) = \eta_F \cdot n_{cell} \cdot \frac{I(t)}{zF} \quad (11)$$

The hydrogen and oxygen produced by the electrolysis process leave the stack as a combination of gas and electrolytic solution. Consequently, it is necessary to separate them from the liquid phase through two horizontal gas-liquid separator vessels – one for the oxygen, and another for the hydrogen. The enthalpy of the produced gas streams can be assumed equal to the enthalpy associated with the water consumption during the electrolysis process [37] (Eq. (12)). Moreover, since the temperature ($T_{sep}(t)$) and the level ($Lvl_{sep}(t)$) in the two separators are the same, the system was treated as if it consisted of a single separator with double the volume and area, along with a singular circulation system for the aqueous solution. The flow rate contributing to the heat exchanges of the system can be considered composed only of a mixture

Table 2

AEL operating parameters at nominal conditions.

Parameter	Unit	Value
Stack target temperature	°C	70
Ambient temperature	°C	25
Stack nominal power	W	2.76×10^6 ^a
AEL nominal power	W	3×10^6
Average electrolyzer efficiency	%	60
Stack pressure	bar	16
Faraday efficiency	%	86
Water consumption	kg/s	0.125
Hydrogen production	Nm ³ /h	554
Oxygen production	Nm ³ /h	277
Specific energy consumption	kWh/Nm ³	4.45

^a The rated power of the stack is calculated as the rated power of the electrolyzer, reduced by 8 % to account for the consumption of the auxiliary systems [36].

of water and electrolyte.

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{\rho}_{lye} \cdot V_{sep} \cdot \bar{c}_{p,lye} \cdot \frac{dT_{sep}(t)}{dt} &= \dot{m}_{lye}(t) \cdot \bar{c}_{p,lye} \cdot T_{stack}(t) - \dot{m}_{sep,out} \cdot \eta_{sep} \\ &\cdot \bar{c}_{p,lye} \cdot T_{sep}(t) - \dot{m}_{wat,cons}(t) \cdot \bar{c}_{p,wat} \cdot T_{stack}(t) - \dot{m}_{lye}(t) \\ &\cdot (1 - \eta_{sep}) \cdot \bar{c}_{p,lye} \cdot T_{sep}(t) - \frac{T_{sep}(t) - T_{amb}}{R_{sep}} \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

where $\bar{\rho}_{lye}$ represents the average density of the electrolyte mixture within the separator (considered to be composed exclusively of water and KOH), V_{sep} is the volume of the separator and has been doubled to take into account both separators. In the present study, for simplicity, the separation efficiency (η_{sep}) of hydrogen and oxygen gas from the aqueous solution is assumed unitary. Therefore, the separation process was considered ideal, so the entrainment losses ($\dot{m}_{lye}(t) \cdot (1 - \eta_{sep}) \cdot \bar{c}_{p,lye} \cdot T_{sep}(t)$) could be neglected.

The filling level of separator vessels represents a relevant control variable since it depends on water consumption in the stack and then on fluctuations of the input renewable power. To prevent the gas-liquid separator from excessively emptying or filling, an ON/OFF level control system is applied to the water make-up pump to keep the separator level within a certain range (0.4 m–0.6 m) for the entire duration of the simulation. The flow rate leaving the separator vessel ($\dot{m}_{sep,out}$) is fixed, while the regulation is made on the make-up water flow rate. After gas separation, the electrolytic mixture enters the mixer, where the consumed water is refilled. The liquid level inside gas-liquid separators is determined through mass balance in Eq. (13):

$$\bar{\rho}_{lye} \cdot 2 \cdot A_{sep} \cdot \frac{dLvl_{sep}(t)}{dt} = \dot{m}_{wat,rein}(t) - \dot{m}_{wat,cons}(t) \quad (13)$$

After the separator, the electrolyte mixture enters the mixer where the water consumed at the stack is refilled. The temperature of the electrolyte mixture coming out of the mixer ($T_{lye,mix,out}(t)$) can be calculated through an enthalpy balance (Eq. (14)):

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{m}_{lye,stack,in}(t) \cdot \bar{c}_{p,lye} \cdot T_{lye,mix,out}(t) &= \dot{m}_{sep,out} \cdot \bar{c}_{p,lye} \cdot T_{sep}(t) \\ &+ \dot{m}_{wat,rein}(t) \cdot c_{p,wat,rein} \cdot T_{wat,rein}(t) \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

Although mixing the electrolyte mixture with low-temperature water (15 °C) does reduce the temperature of the electrolyte mixture, it is insufficient to achieve the desired stack temperature. Consequently, a cooling system with temperature control becomes necessary. The regulation is implemented to maintain the stack temperature consistently close to the target value of 70 °C.

The cooler was modeled as an ideal component (Eq. (15)):

$$\begin{aligned} Q_{cool}(t) &= \dot{m}_{lye} \cdot \bar{c}_{p,lye} \cdot (T_{lye,mix,out}(t) - T_{lye,cool,out}(t)) \\ &= C_{wat,cool} \cdot (T_{wat,cool,out}(t) - T_{wat,cool,in}(t)) = UA_{HX} \cdot LMTD \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

Table 3
MU operating parameters.

Parameter	Unit	Value
mol H ₂ : mol CO ₂	–	4:1
Pressure	bar	16
Methanation efficiency at nominal conditions	%	80 [27]
Load of methanation	%	40–100 [27]
Load change rate of methanation	%/min	±10 [27]
Nominal hydrogen volume flow	Nm ³ /h	1773
Nominal methane production	Nm ³ /h	439

Fig. 3. Example of operation of the MU management strategy. The grey area represents the permissible operating points of the MU at each timestep.

where $C_{\text{wat,cool}}$ is the thermal capacity of the cooling water and $T_{\text{wat,cool,in}}(t)$ and $T_{\text{wat,cool,out}}(t)$ are computed through an iterative process.

The efficiency of the electrolyzer is defined as (Eq. (16)):

$$\eta_{\text{AEL}}(t) = \frac{\dot{m}_{\text{H}_2,\text{AEL}}(t) \cdot \text{LHV}_{\text{H}_2}}{P_{\text{AEL}}(t)} \quad (16)$$

The utilization factor for the electrolyzer is defined as (Eq. (17)):

$$\text{UF}_{\text{AEL}}(t) = \frac{h_{\text{eq,AEL}}(t)}{h(t)} \cdot 100 \quad (17)$$

where $h_{\text{eq,AEL}}$ is the equivalent operating hours of the electrolyzer, and h is the total duration of the simulation expressed in hours.

The utilization factor for the ES is defined as (Eq. (18)):

$$\text{UF}_{\text{ES}}(t) = \frac{\sum_{n_{\text{AEL}}=1}^4 h_{\text{eq,AEL}}(t, n_{\text{AEL}})}{4 \cdot h(t)} \cdot 100 \quad (18)$$

2.2.1.3. Operation at nominal conditions. By simulating the operation of a single electrolyzer fed with nominal power, the obtained results are close to those obtained in the reference study [36], whose model is experimentally validated. In Table 2, the main operating parameters of the electrolyzer are given.

Table 4
Sensitivity analysis parameters.

Parameter	Unit	Values
MUsize	%	40 60 80 100
	Nm ³ /h	887 1,330 1,773 2,217
HS size	h	1 10 100
	Nm ³	2,217 22,170 221,700

2.2.2. Hydrogen storage

The HS is considered an ideal component, and it is modeled as a variable volume at constant pressure (16 bar). Its storage capacity is 4434 Nm³ of hydrogen, corresponding to the amount of hydrogen required by the MU to operate continuously for two-and-a-half hours at nominal conditions and it achieves SOC = 100% from SOC = 0% in 2 h when powered by the ES system at a constant hydrogen flow rate matching its nominal production $\dot{V}_{\text{H}_2,\text{ES,out,max}}$.

The number of equivalent charge/discharge cycles of the HS can be defined as (Eq. (19)):

$$N_{\text{eq,cycles,HS}}(t) = \frac{\left| \sum_{i=1}^t \Delta \text{SOC}_{\text{dis}}(i) \right| + \left| \sum_{i=1}^t \Delta \text{SOC}_{\text{ch}}(i) \right|}{2} \quad (19)$$

2.2.3. Methanation unit

The MU is modeled in Matlab without going into the thermodynamic details of its operation. The model provides the methane flow rate based on the feeding hydrogen according to stoichiometry.

The MU is assumed to operate in a range of 40–100% of the nominal flow rate, without major changes in the quality of the produced gas, with a maximum load change rate of ±10%/min [27]. The main operating parameters of the MU are reported in Table 3. Since the electricity input might fluctuate strongly and electrolyzers and the MU work at different loads, it is necessary to decouple the two components. For this purpose, HS is added between the electrolyzer and the MU, and it is modeled as an ideal component. In this study, the MU, the ES, and the HS are considered at the same pressure (16 bar). However, compressing hydrogen after the ES could significantly decrease the storage volume. The methane flow rate is retrieved from the methanation efficiency according to Eq. (20).

$$\eta_{\text{met}}(t) = \frac{\text{LHV}_{\text{CH}_4} \cdot \dot{m}_{\text{CH}_4}(t)}{\text{LHV}_{\text{H}_2} \cdot \dot{m}_{\text{H}_2,\text{in,met}}(t)} \cdot 100 \quad (20)$$

The utilization factor for the MU is defined as in Eq. (21):

$$\text{UF}_{\text{met}}(t) = \frac{h_{\text{eq,met}}(t)}{h(t)} \cdot 100 \quad (21)$$

3. Management algorithms

3.1. Electrolysis system

The power generated by the wind farm supplies an ES of the same overall nominal power (12 MW). Due to the variability of the renewable source, the wind farm rarely produces its nominal power. For this reason, a management algorithm is developed to ensure that the four electrolyzers have averagely similar performances in terms of number of shutdowns, equivalent operating hours and hydrogen production. Three operational states are defined as follows:

- ON: the electrolyzer is operating, and the input power is equally distributed among the operational electrolyzers.
- OFF: the electrolyzer is inactive, drawing zero power, and consequently no hydrogen is produced. To prevent frequent ON-OFF cycles that could lead to rapid degradation of system components, a

Fig. 4. Power distribution between the four electrolyzers during a daily simulation (September 25) [30].

Table 5

Performances of the four electrolyzers in a daily simulation (September 25).

Electrolyzer	Efficiency (%)	Hydrogen production (Nm ³)	Utilization factor (%)	Number of shutdowns (-)	Oxygen production (Nm ³)	Water consumption (kg)	Average stack temperature (°C)	Maximum duration of the OFF period (h)
1	60.30	10,619	79.59	1	5283	8532	70.5	0.5
2	60.07	6388	48.02	2	3171	5133	67.9	8.6
3	60.28	10,993	82.05	1	5470	8833	70.1	0.5
4	60.26	8716	65.37	3	4333	7003	69.6	1.8
ES	-	36,716	-	-	18,258	29,500	-	-

Fig. 5. Performance of the management strategy for the MU and HS during a two-day simulation (March 22–23) [30].

minimum shutdown duration of 1 h is enforced before the electrolyzer can switch back to the ON state.

- Standby (SB): this state represents the readiness for use. While in this state, the electrolyzer does not produce hydrogen, a control system maintains the stack temperature above a minimum value of 60 °C to ensure the leak-tightness of the electrolyzer block [18]. From the SB state, the electrolyzer can return to the ON state at any time through a half-hour shutdown period. If it does not resume the ON state after this period, the electrolyzer switches off.

The management algorithm ensures that each electrolyzer works always within its operative range (20–100% of its nominal power).

Indicating $P_{RE}(t)$ as the renewable input power, $P_{NOM,ES}$ as the

nominal power of the ES (12 MW), and $P_{NOM,AEL}$ as the nominal power of a single electrolyzer, the following three conditions can occur depending on $P_{RE}(t)$:

- $P_{RE}(t) < 20\% \cdot P_{NOM,AEL}$: all electrolyzers are turned off. The hydrogen production is zero and the electricity from the wind field is not utilized by the ES.
- $20\% \cdot P_{NOM,AEL} \leq P_{RE}(t) \leq P_{NOM,ES}$: the number of operating electrolyzers is determined to maximize the utilization of available input power. The input power is evenly distributed among the operating electrolyzers.

In the operating range of the ES, the operational state of each

Table 6

Performances of the MU and the HS system for four seasonal typical days (December 21, September 25, March 22, and June 21).

Day	Methane production (Nm ³)	Number of equivalent charge/ discharge cycles (-)	MU utilization factor (%)	Surplus hydrogen (Nm ³)	Number of shutdowns (-)
21-Dec	10,538	0	100.00	10,539	0
25-Sep	8831	32.88	83.80	0	0
22-Mar	6952	46.69	65.96	76	1
21-Jun	5014	31.74	47.58	0	1

Fig. 6. Performances of the P2G system during four seasonal characteristic days: a) December 21; b) September 25; c) March 22; d) June 21 [30].

electrolyzer at each time step is established according to the management rules and constraints based on the following parameters:

- The operational state of the electrolyzer at the previous timestep: the control algorithm aims to maintain the electrolyzer state to avoid unnecessary transitions between operating states, while respecting operating conditions;
- The equivalent operating hours: the algorithm ensures even distribution among the four electrolyzers;
- The duration of the OFF state (with a minimum of 1 h);
- The duration of the SB state (with a maximum half an hour);

If a change in the electrolyzer state is necessary, the following criteria are followed:

- If the wind power is not enough to feed all the electrolyzers in operation, one or more electrolyzers need to transition from the ON state to the SB state, and then the algorithm selects the electrolyzers with the highest operating hours.

- If wind power exceeds the nominal power of operating electrolyzers, one or more electrolyzers need to transition to the ON state. Priority is given to the electrolyzers that have been in SB for the longest time. If further electrolyzers need to be turned ON from the OFF state, the algorithm selects the electrolyzers with fewer operating hours, but only if it has been in the OFF state for more than 1 h.
- After a maximum SB duration of half an hour, the electrolyzer is turned OFF unless it transitions to the ON state.

3.2. Methanation unit and hydrogen storage

The hydrogen flow rate feeding the MU is often different from its nominal flow rate depending on the power supplied by the wind farm. Depending on the size of the MU, during the simulations, the ES could produce a certain amount of hydrogen which cannot be converted into methane. For this reason, a management strategy for hydrogen surplus is needed.

In a previous study [38], three management strategies were implemented and compared to identify the most affected parameters and how the system performance varies based on these strategies. Specifically,

Table 7

Performances of an AEL for four seasonal typical days (December 21, September 25, March 22, and June 21).

Day	Feed water system at the ON state (%)	Stack average temperature(°C)	Average efficiency (%)	Cooling system at the ON state (%)	Hydrogen production (Nm ³)	Utilization factor (%)
21-Dec	100.00	73.9	59.86	89	13,316	99.92
25-Sep	64.36	70.0	61.85	63	9380	68.79
22-Mar	52.25	68.0	66.91	52	7964	59.46
21-Jun	32.52	69.2	63.15	38	5569	42.01

Fig. 7. Performance of the cooling system during four seasonal characteristic days: a) December 21, b) September 25, c) March 22, and d) June 21. In the figure, '1' represents the 'ON' state, while '0' represents the 'OFF' state [30].

the selected management strategy (management strategy B) is the one that minimizes the number of shutdowns of the MU while ensuring, at the same time, high methane production. This management strategy is employed in the current work.

The logic of the management strategy can be summarized as follows: if the hydrogen flow rate from the ES exceeds the nominal feed flow rate of the MU, the MU works at maximum load, and hydrogen produced in excess is stored into the HS (Fig. 3, timesteps "i+1"). On the other hand, if the produced hydrogen is lower than the minimum flow rate of methanation, the MU is set to its minimum load, and the storage provides the missing hydrogen (Fig. 3, timesteps "i-1"). When the ES has higher load change rates than those tolerable by the MU, the HS acts as a "ramps mitigator" (Fig. 3, timestep "i+2"). When the hydrogen flow rate produced by the ES allows the MU to operate within the allowed load range, the hydrogen feed flow rate can be increased or decreased (if $SOC > SOC_{target}$ or $SOC < SOC_{target}$ respectively) to let the state of charge of the storage approach its target value (SOC_{target}), set to 50%.

The HS, therefore, has the function of absorbing the off-range hydrogen production peaks, keeping the ramps within the constraints imposed on the load change rate of the MU. However, hydrogen can be stored only until the HS reaches the full-charge status, after which the surplus hydrogen can no longer be stored, and we could have hydrogen losses.

To avoid an excessive number of shutdowns of the MU during less windy seasons, a minimum SOC constraint is imposed for the restart of the MU after shutdowns. Especially during less windy seasons, the hydrogen

Fig. 8. Performances of the separators level control system during four seasonal characteristic days: a) December 21, b) September 25, c) March 22, and d) June 21. In the figure, '1' represents the 'ON' state, while '0' represents the 'OFF' state [30].

production is not enough to ensure continuous operation of the MU at minimum load. Therefore, allowing hydrogen withdrawal from the HS whenever needed would cause excessive ON-OFF cycles of the MU since the low hydrogen production and low SOC of the HS cannot support the continuous operation of the system. Setting a minimum SOC ($SOC_{min} = 50\%$) before the MU can be turned on again after a shutdown allows the system to reach the conditions that support the MU for a longer period, limiting its shutdowns and, consequently, its degradation.

4. Sensitivity analysis

The selection of the MU size can be based on the value of the produced hydrogen flow rate that most often occurs during the year. In the considered case, this value corresponds to the maximum value of hydrogen production. However, this criterion may lead to overestimating the capacities of the MU and the HS. As highlighted in a previous study [38], there is a need to investigate more deeply the impact of the subsystem sizes on the overall system performance.

To address this gap, after conducting the simulation for fixed sizes of all the subsystems, a sensitivity analysis on the sizes of the MU and HS is performed to determine their impact on the following performance indicators of the P2G system:

- Methane production;
- Utilization factor of the MU;
- Number of equivalent charge/discharge cycles of the HS;
- Number of annual MU shutdowns;
- Hydrogen surplus;
- Annual average load of the MU during its operation.

Table 8

Performances of the four electrolyzers at the end of a one-year simulation.

Electrolyzer	Efficiency (%)	Hydrogen production (Nm ³)	Utilization factor (%)	Number of shutdowns (–)	Water consumption (kg)	Stack temperature (°C)	Maximum duration of the OFF period (h)
1	60.95	1,597,493	32.67	537	1,283,546	66.5	62
2	60.93	1,598,248	32.69	548	1,284,152	66.3	62
3	60.85	1,595,090	32.67	541	1,281,615	66.2	64
4	60.94	1,597,295	32.69	546	1,283,387	66.6	56
ES	–	6,388,126	–	–	5,132,700	–	–

Table 9

Performances of the MU in a one-year simulation.

Methane production (Nm ³)	Surplus hydrogen (Nm ³)	Utilization factor (%)	Number of shutdowns (–)	Maximum duration of the OFF period (h)	Percentage of time in the ON state (%)	Percentage of time at the minimum load (%)	Percentage of time at the maximum load (%)
1,542,389	154,949	40.10	301	114	62.74	24.88	16.35

Table 10

Performances of the HS in a one-year simulation.

Percentage of time that SOC < SOC _{target} (%)	Number of equivalent charge/discharge cycles (–)
77.42	17,266

The sensitivity analysis is carried out by combining three sizes of the HS system and four sizes of the MU, resulting in twelve combinations (see Table 4).

For the sake of generality, the size of the MU is expressed in terms of its nominal hydrogen flow rate as a percentage of the nominal hydrogen flow rate of the ES ($\dot{V}_{H_2, \text{nom, ES}} = 2,216 \text{ Nm}^3/\text{h}$), while the size of the HS system is expressed in terms of the time required to reach SOC = 100% from SOC = 0% with an incoming flow rate of $\dot{V}_{H_2, \text{nom, ES}}$.

5. Results and discussion

In the first phase, daily simulations were carried out; then, a second set of simulations were performed on four typical days characterizing the seasonal trend of the wind: December 21, September 25, March 22, and June 21. The chosen typical days are solstices and equinoxes, or days close to solstices and equinoxes, when the wind speed data have an untypical trend.

5.1. Daily performances

Fig. 4 shows the power distribution among the four electrolyzers of the ES during a daily simulation (September 25). The sizing of the ES and the number of separated electrolyzers was such to ensure the utilization of all the available renewable power while respecting the constraints imposed on the electrolyzers.

On a daily basis, the four electrolyzers exhibited different performances in terms of hydrogen production, utilization factor, number of shutdowns, water consumption and maximum duration of the OFF period (see Table 5). This happens because constraints imposed to AELs through the ES management strategy (e.g.: minimum shutdown duration and maximum SB duration) make it difficult to appreciate the effects of the management algorithm on a daily basis. However, the effectiveness of the management strategy became noticeable on a yearly basis, as shown in Section 5.2.

Regarding the whole P2G system, Fig. 5 shows the operation of the management algorithm for the MU and HS during a two-day simulation. Until 4 p.m. on the first day, the SOC of the HS was under 50%; then, a certain share of the produced hydrogen incoming from the ES was used to fill the HS, while the remaining flow rate was sent to the MU to be converted into methane.

From 4 p.m. of the first day, the SOC of the HS was over 50%; in particular, approximately from 8:30 p.m.–10 p.m. on the first day and

2:30 a.m.–5 a.m. on the second day, the produced hydrogen and a certain share from the HS were sent to the MU.

During the remaining period, the produced hydrogen rate was out of the constraints of the MU; indeed, the MU was set to the maximum load or switched off, and the surplus hydrogen was stored up to the filling limit of the HS. The performances of the MU and the HS for four seasonal typical days are given in Table 6.

In Fig. 6, the characteristic variable trends of the P2G system during four seasonal characteristic days are shown. The hydrogen flow rates and the methane production were expressed as percentages of the nominal hydrogen production of the ES and the nominal production of the MU ($\dot{V}_{CH_4, \text{nom}} = 439 \text{ Nm}^3/\text{h}$), respectively.

Similarly to the ES, the results for the daily performances of the P2G system showed seasonal differences, with higher methane production in the windiest season, from which derives a most intensive use of the MU.

During the summer (Fig. 6d), the SOC of the HS was averagely lower than in the other seasons, and this is due to the poorer wind conditions, which made the MU work at a relatively low average load (and low MU utilization factor) and the hydrogen production rate be often below the minimum feed rate for the MU. In this condition, the MU needs hydrogen from the HS to be able to continue to work at least at its minimum load. When the HS is empty, it can no longer supply hydrogen to the MU. This result in frequent shutdowns and a non-continuous operation of the MU.

On the other hand, on windy days (Fig. 6a and b) the MU had a high utilization factor, and, in some periods, also exceeded the upper limit value. When the hydrogen production from the ES is higher than the nominal inlet flow rate of the MU and the MU is set to the nominal working point, if the HS SOC is 100% a certain share of the produced hydrogen cannot be converted into methane or stored. This condition mainly occurred during the winter, when the highest share of surplus hydrogen could be observed (see Fig. 6a).

In Table 7 the performances of a single AEL during four seasonal typical days are given. During windy days (December 21 and September 25) the cooling system was in the ON state for almost all the day (see Fig. 7). This happens because a higher windiness implies a more intensive use of the electrolyzer and, consequently, a higher heat generation. Similarly, the separator level control system showed a longer working time of the make-up feed water system in winter and autumn (see Fig. 8). However, both the stack temperature and the separator level were always within the required range ($70 \pm 5 \text{ °C}$ and $50 \pm 10\%$ of the separator height, respectively), which is a sign that the applied control systems ensure the desired management of the AEL.

5.2. Annual performances

In the second phase of this study, an annual simulation was carried out on the P2G system. Contrary to what the results of the daily simulations suggested, on a yearly basis, the electrolyzers exhibited similar

Fig. 9. Radar plot illustrating the performance indicators' trends¹ across varying sizes of the MU with fixed sizes of the HS: a) 1h; b) 10h; c) 100h.

¹ Note that a value close to 10 for the surplus hydrogen and MU annual number of shutdowns parameters indicates a positive impact on the performance of the P2G system, hence a lower quantity of the parameter in absolute terms.

behavior and comparable performances in terms of all the observed variables (see Table 8).

In Table 9 and Table 10, the performances of the MU and the HS at the end of the one-year simulation are shown, respectively. Only 2.4% of the produced hydrogen was in surplus. In addition, the use of HS and the adopted management strategy effectively decreased the annual number of MU shutdowns from 1006 to 301.

Overall, the management strategies adopted both for the ES and for the MU adequately managed to operate the P2G system minimizing the yearly surplus of hydrogen while ensuring a limited number of shutdowns that would otherwise increase the system degradation.

5.3. Sensitivity analysis

As a conclusion of the study, a sensitivity analysis was conducted on the sizes of the MU and the HS to examine how the sizes of the subsystems impact the overall performance of the P2G system. The size of the ES remained fixed and equal to the size of the wind farm.

The performance indicators that were selected as representative of the system performance are: methane production, surplus hydrogen, number of charge/discharge equivalent cycles, MU average load, annual number of shutdowns, MU utilization factor (see Fig. 9a–c).

In Fig. 9, the normalized values of the performance indicators can be observed for different sizes of the MU, while maintaining a constant size for the HS.

To make a comparison, the selected performance indicators have been normalized according to the normalization criteria given in the Appendix. The comparison range was from 0 to 10, where 0 indicates a poor system performance for the selected indicator and 10 indicates a high system performance for the selected indicator.

The annual hydrogen surplus strongly decreased (while the normalized indicator increased) with the increase in the size of the MU, as an increasing percentage of hydrogen from the ES can be directly converted into methane without passing through the intermediate HS, and the HS is less frequently completely full. However, a larger MU led to a reduction in its average load and utilization factor, so choosing MU sizes close to the ES one would result in over-sizing.

The number of equivalent charge/discharge cycles of the smallest HS increased with increasing sizes of the MU reaching normalized values near 10. Nevertheless, varying the size of the MU did not have a significant influence on the number of equivalent cycles for larger sizes of the storage.

In addition, the annual number of shutdowns of the MU increased (while the normalized indicator decreased) with the increase in the size of the MU. This is because large MUs are more affected by the variability of the wind source. However, this effect can be mitigated proportionally to the size of the HS in between.

Results given in Fig. 10 show that increasing sizes of the HS had progressively a less significant impact on the performance of the system in terms of methane production, surplus hydrogen, and utilization factor for increasing sizes of the MU. This happens because, by using a larger MU, the HS stores hydrogen only if the production from the ES is lower than the minimum flow rate of methanation. On the other hand, the other indicators varied considerably with the size of the HS for all the considered MU sizes.

Particularly for small sizes of the MU, using a larger HS improved the performance of the P2G system according to all the considered performance indicators, except for the MU average load (which decreased slightly with the HS size) and the number of equivalent charge/discharge cycles of the HS. This implies that, for a given MU size, there is an optimal HS size after which an increase in HS size does not lead to a proportional increase in P2G system performances.

A qualitative criterion to identify the optimal sizes of the subsystems is choosing the sizes for which the hexagon in the radar plot subtends the largest area. In Table 11, the twelve analyzed cases ordered in descending order from top to bottom based on this criterion are given.

Fig. 10. Radar plot illustrating the performance indicators' trends across varying sizes of the HS with fixed sizes of the MU: a) 40%; b) 60%; c) 80%; d) 100%.

Table 11
Analyzed cases ordered in descending order of area subtended by their hexagon in the radar plot, from top to bottom.

MU size (%)	HS size (h)
80	1
100	1
40	100
60	100
60	10
60	1
40	10
80	10
80	100
100	10
100	100
40	1

According to this ranking criterion, the choice should be oriented towards the smallest HS (storage capacity of 2217 Nm³ of hydrogen, corresponding to the amount of hydrogen required to achieve SOC = 100% in 1 h when fed with ES nominal hydrogen production) and towards a size of the MU equal to 80% (1773 Nm³/h) of the ES nominal production (2216 Nm³/h), and this result validates the initial sizing. Nonetheless, results in Table 11 did not show a significant trend, neither for the HS size, nor for the MU.

It should be pointed out that this ranking is highly dependent on the selected indicators, but also on the chosen management strategy and on the input wind power. However, this method can also be applied to different sizes and case studies.

Another analyzed factor is the presence of the constraint imposing the value of the SOC_{min} for turning on the MU after shutdown. Fig. 11 shows the impact of this constraint on the P2G system. This constraint did not impact significantly any of the performance indicators, except for the annual number of shutdowns of the MU.

Fig. 12 shows that applying this constraint drastically reduced differences in the annual number of shutdowns among all the twelve analyzed cases.

In the selected case study, the annual number of MU shutdowns would have been 5950 without this constraint, instead of 301 with the imposed constraint.

However, in this analysis, no weights have been assigned to the considered performance indicators to define their actual impact on the P2G system, and this can be considered the major limitation of this analysis.

6. Summary and conclusions

In this study, a mathematical model of a P2G system for methane production from wind source was developed. The system comprises an ES, composed of four AELs, powered solely by a 12 MW wind farm, an HS and an MU. The HS was designed for two-and-a-half hours of independent operation of the MU, while the nominal input hydrogen flow rate of the MU is equal to 80% of the hydrogen nominal production of the ES.

Management strategies were adopted for the AELs and the HS to limit the fluctuating and discontinuous operation of both the ES and the MU. The management strategy of the ES was conceived to averagely ensure similar operating conditions for the four AELs. The management strategy proposed for the HS ensured a limited number of shutdowns of the MU while minimizing the surplus of hydrogen.

Results over four seasonal typical days revealed a more intensive use of the electrolyzers, the MU, and the HS in windy seasons.

By performing an annual simulation, only 2.4% of the hydrogen produced was in surplus and the number of shutdowns of the MU turned out to be drastically reduced by the presence of the HS.

To assess the impact of the sizes of subsystems on the overall performance of the P2G system, a sensitivity analysis was conducted on the sizes of the MU and the HS. Moreover, a constraint of a minimum SOC of 50% to be reached was imposed for turning on the MU after a shutdown.

Fig. 11. Radar plot illustrating the performance indicators' trends across varying sizes of the HS of the MU; comparison between the cases without (a) and with (b) the SOC_{min} constraint.

Fig. 12. Comparison of the annual number of MU shutdowns in cases without (a) and with (b) the SOC_{min} constraint.

This constraint effectively drastically reduced the number of annual shutdowns in all the considered cases, without affecting the other performance indicators of the P2G system.

The results of the sensitivity analysis showed that increasing the size of the MU would decrease the annual hydrogen surplus, and, consequently, increase the annual methane production. Nevertheless, using a

larger MU would imply a reduction in its average load and utilization factor, and an increase in the annual number of MU shutdowns. In addition, the number of equivalent charge/discharge cycles of the smallest HS increased with increasing sizes of the MU, but this trend cannot be observed for higher sizes of the HS.

Large sizes of the HS lead to better performances of the MU in terms of annual methane production, annual surplus hydrogen, annual number of shutdowns, and utilization factor, while working with a slightly lower average load. In addition, increasing the size of the HS decreases its number of equivalent charge/discharge cycles, resulting in HS oversizing.

The sensitivity analysis suggested selecting the smallest size of the HS (storage capacity of 2217 Nm³ of hydrogen, corresponding to 1 h to be filled when fed with ES nominal hydrogen production) and a size of the MU equal to 80% of the ES nominal production.

It is important to note that this categorization depends significantly on the chosen indicators, the selected management strategy and the input power, as well as on the possibility of valorizing the hydrogen surplus.

A partial limitation of this analysis is that no weights have been assigned to the considered performance indicators to define their actual impact on the P2G. An analysis of costs associated with the P2G could be useful to establish the optimal size of the subsystems to maximize the system profitability, also introducing a comparison with alternative energy options.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Valeria Pignataro: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Angelica Liponi:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Eleonora Bargiacchi:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Lorenzo Ferrari:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Formal analysis, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Nomenclature

AEL	Alkaline Electrolyzer
CCU	Carbon Capture Utilization
ES	Electrolysis System
HS	Hydrogen Storage
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
LHV	Lower Heating Value, J/kg
MU	Methanation Unit
NREL	National Renewable Energy Laboratory
P2F	Power to Fuel
P2G	Power to Gas
P2L	Power to Liquid
RES	Renewable Energy Sources
S2F	Solar to Fuel
SNG	Synthetic Natural Gas
SOC	State Of Charge

Symbols

C	thermal capacity, J/K
\bar{c}_p	average specific heat at constant pressure, J/(kg K)
E	voltage, V
F	Faraday constant, C/mol
I	current intensity, A
\dot{m}	mass flow rate, kg/s
n	number, -
p	pressure, bar
P	power, W
Q	heat flow, W
T	temperature, °C
\dot{V}	volumetric flow rate, m ³ /s

Greek symbol

η	efficiency, %
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Subscripts

act	activation
AEL	Alkaline Electrolyzer
amb	ambient environment
cap	capacity
cell	electrolyzer cell
ch,cycle	charge cycle
cool	cooler
cons	consumed at the stack
dis,cycle	discharge cycle
eq	equivalent
ES	Electrolysis System
F	Faraday
gen	generated inside the stack
in	at the inlet
loss	losses
met	methanation unit
min	minimum
mix	mixer
nom	nominal value
NORM	normalized
ohm	ohmic
out	at the outlet
rein	reintegration
rev	reversible
sep	gas-liquid separator
sys	system
stack	within the stack
target	target value
tn	thermoneutral
wat	water

Appendix

The selected performance indicators (Figs. 9, 10 and 11) have been normalized according to the following definitions:

$$M_{\text{year,CH}_4,\text{NORM}} = \frac{M_{\text{year,CH}_4}}{\text{MAX}\left(\left(M_{\text{year,CH}_4}\right)_i\right)} \bullet 10 \quad (\text{A.1})$$

$$N_{\text{eq,cycles,HS,NORM}} = \frac{N_{\text{eq,cycles,HS}}}{\text{MAX}\left(\left(N_{\text{eq,cycles,HS}}\right)_i\right)} \bullet 10 \quad (\text{A.2})$$

$$UF_{\text{year,met,NORM}} = \frac{UF_{\text{year,met}}}{10} \quad (\text{A.3})$$

$$AL_{\text{year,met,NORM}} = \frac{AL_{\text{year,met}}}{10} \quad (\text{A.4})$$

$$M_{\text{year,H}_2,\text{surplus,NORM}} = 10 - \frac{M_{\text{year,H}_2,\text{surplus}} \cdot 10}{\text{MAX}\left(\left(M_{\text{year,H}_2,\text{surplus}}\right)_i\right)} \quad (\text{A.5})$$

$$N_{\text{year,shutdowns,NORM}} = 10 - \frac{N_{\text{year,shutdowns}} \cdot 10}{\text{MAX}\left(\left(N_{\text{year,shutdowns}}\right)_i\right)} \quad (\text{A.6})$$

where $M_{\text{year,CH}_4}$, $M_{\text{year,H}_2,\text{surplus}}$ and $N_{\text{year,shutdowns}}$ are, respectively, the annual methane production, the annual hydrogen surplus, and the annual number of shutdowns of the MU, while the denominator of Eq. (A.1), Eq. (A.2), Eq. (A.5) and Eq. (A.6) represents the maximum value assumed by the considered indicators among the examined cases (denoted by index i). $UF_{\text{year,met}}$ and $AL_{\text{year,met}}$ are, respectively, the annual utilization factor and the annual average load of the MU, while $N_{\text{eq,cycles,HS}}$ is the number of equivalent charge/discharge cycles of the HS.

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